

**IMPLEMENTATION OF FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTS OF
EMPLOYEES IN DIFFERENT GENERATIONAL DIVIDES:
ITS RELATIONSHIP ON THE CLIENT'S SATISFACTION
AS PERCEIVED BY THE EMPLOYEES
AND DEPARTMENT HEAD**

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Implementation of Flexible Work Arrangements of Employees in Different Generational Divides: Its Relationship on the Client's Satisfaction as Perceived by the Employees and Department Head

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of implementing flexible work arrangements (FWAs) on client satisfaction and non-teaching personnel's productivity within a diverse generational workforce context as perceived by the Heads and employees themselves. With changing workplace dynamics influenced by varying generational perceptions and preferences, organizations are increasingly adopting Flexible Work Arrangements to accommodate different employee needs. This research investigates how Flexible Work Arrangement (FWA), tailored to specific generational groups (such as Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z), influences client satisfaction levels regarding the productivity of non-teaching personnel in this educational institution. This research used a Likert-scale quantitative survey to gather comprehensive data. Responses from the head and personnel of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City assess changes in client satisfaction and productivity metrics following the adoption of the Flexible Work Arrangement. The findings reveal the connection between implementing Flexible Work Arrangements in different generational divides and their subsequent impact on client satisfaction and non-teaching personnel's productivity. The analysis identifies correlations between Flexible Work Arrangement satisfaction levels, service quality perceptions, and non-teaching staff productivity indicators. Ultimately, this research contributes to understanding the role of Flexible Work Arrangements in the development of positive organizational outcomes amidst generational diversity. By uncovering the relationship between flexible work arrangements and client satisfaction and non-teaching personnel productivity perceived by the head and employees, this study informs strategic human resource decisions to optimize workplace flexibility and enhance overall organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: *flexible work arrangements, different generational divides, satisfaction*

Introduction

Under CSC Resolution No. 2200209 promulgated on 18 May 2022, the Commission adopts the following Policies on Flexible Work Arrangements in the Government to institutionalize relevant and appropriate work arrangements for government officials and employees to ensure efficient and effective performance of governmental functions and delivery of public services, and to ensure protection of their health, safety, and welfare always.

In an ideal situation, employees should have a balance between work and personal life commitments. A flexible work arrangement (FWA) allows an employee to have the freedom to choose the time when they can begin to work and when they will stop working. According to Ability Options, Flexible working arrangements allow employees to negotiate a less rigid working arrangement to improve work-life balance and their overall contribution to their company. The Organization would then have optimum productivity.

According to the Bureau of Labor Statistics, productivity is a measure of economic performance that compares the number of goods and services produced (output) with the number of inputs used to produce those goods and services. In a National Agency set up, specifically in the Department of Education, productivity refers to how well you deliver excellent public service to meet the unique and immediate needs of both teaching and non-teaching personnel to contribute indirectly to the mission of the Organization in giving quality and complete basic education to the learners.

Each perception of productivity may be identical to completing the to-do lists in a day or accomplishing their main tasks for the day or the week. The efficiency of an employee depends on how he or she perceives it. The reality is that not all tasks are equal. Tasks may vary depending on the position and the nature of the work to be done. The weight of the tasks is also affected by different factors, and one of these is the demographic profile, which includes gender and age, which incorporates a different view of productivity. Aside from the individual views, the head of the Organization, the managers, or the unit heads can see if their subordinate perform their duties and responsibilities well.

Aside from the different perceptions of the employees regarding productivity, their immediate heads would be the perfect person to ask because they directly monitor their subordinates. Their evaluation would be the most accurate and helpful information that can be used as they could see how well their employees perform. With this, superiors' perceptions would be important feedback for the personnel to be considered productive. The data that will be gathered could be the key to a much more fruitful Division of San Pedro City. As Flexible Work Arrangements have been implemented in the Department of Education Schools Division Office of San Pedro City, this study aims to determine if there is a relationship between the implemented flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides and the satisfaction of all clients of the Division Office of San Pedro City as evaluated by themselves

and their Department Heads. After this study, we will be able to find if the flexible work arrangement is effective in connection with the productivity of the personnel of the Division Office of San Pedro City.

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the implementation of flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides on the client's satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity as perceived by themselves and their Department heads. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their generational divide?
2. What is the level of the client's satisfaction of the Selected Employees of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City as perceived by Department Heads and themselves in terms of:
 - 3.1 responsiveness;
 - 3.2 reliability;
 - 3.3 communication;
 - 3.4 integrity; and
 - 3.5 outcome?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the different levels of the employee's generational divide in the client's satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the flexible work arrangement implementation in the client's satisfaction with Schools Division Office of San Pedro's non-teaching personnel's productivity?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the correlational method of research to determine the relationship between the implementation of flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides on the client's satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City as perceived by the employees themselves and their Department heads. According to Leedy et al. (2013), correlational research is concerned with establishing relationships between two or more variables in the same population or between the same variables in two populations. This study used this method to obtain a general synopsis that described and interpreted the subject. Since it was concerned with conditions of relationship that exist, effects were developed, and the causes of particular phenomena at the time this study was conducted. It sets out to identify the relationship of the given variables and aims to come up with the result whether if the variables have a relationship, it will help to understand the real relationships of the variables present in the study.

Participants

The study focused on the relationship between the implementation of flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides on the non-teaching personnel's self-assessment and their department heads' evaluation of productivity.

This study is conducted on all employees of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. It covers seventy-nine (79) population of non-teaching personnel which includes the Department Heads of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. The focus of the study is the employees of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City because the researcher identified that this Schools Division Office has implemented this flexible work arrangement for several months already. The whole population was selected primarily because it is suited to the consideration that the study is looking for, a workplace that implements a flexible work arrangement.

The respondents are selected by using purposive sampling. At the time, the actual correlational study was conducted to use as a sample respondent on the present study from seventy-nine (79) Schools Division Office of San Pedro City non-teaching personnel which includes the Department Heads of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City.

Instruments

The researcher used a questionnaire-rating scale to determine the relationship of the implementation of flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides on the client's satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City as perceived by the employees themselves and their Department heads.

A specific questionnaire adapted and modified by the researcher was used in the study and validated by different experts. The researcher used pen and paper and Google Forms for the questionnaire, and it was answered by clicking their choice in the space provided, the evidence of the respondents' rating prior to the given statements was based on their perception and their own experience in their place.

Procedure

The researcher got the whole population of non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City working in a flexible work arrangement. The researcher used Purposive Sampling specifically the Total population sampling as all the Schools

Division Office’s Non-Teaching Personnel are working under Flexible Work Arrangement. The researcher adapted and modified the questionnaire and validated it by experts before it was distributed through a pen-and-paper questionnaire. The approval of the Schools Division Superintendent was also sought by the respondents as a courtesy for the implementation of the study. After the collection of data, it was analyzed, presented, and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

The approval of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City is a courtesy for the implementation and completion of the study. In the questionnaire, the name is optional to give the respondents freedom if they prefer to place their identity directly. Their demographic profile is collected in line with the age bracket which falls in its respective generational divides. This research also assures the security and confidentiality of the respondents and their answers to the questionnaire that the information gathered will be used solely for the study. There is a clear explanation of the scope and purpose of the research in each of the clients to help them understand the sole persistence of the conduct of the study.

Data Analysis

The weighted mean and standard deviation were applied in this study and Pearson R was used to determine the relationship between the relationship of implementation of flexible work arrangements of employees in different generational divides on the client’s satisfaction to non-teaching personnel’s productivity.

The statistical treatment used in the study was chosen by the researcher based on the related literature gathered. To determine the significant relationship in the rating made by the seventy-nine (79) respondents from the SDO San Pedro employees, the researcher used the Pearson correlation coefficient, often referred to as the Pearson r test formula as a basis for correlational testing and null hypothesis at 5 percent significant level.

Pearson correlation is the test statistics that measures the statistical relationship, or association, between two continuous variables. It is known as the best method of measuring the association between variables of interest because it is based on the method of covariance. It gives information about the magnitude of the association, or correlation, as well as the direction of the relationship.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents. Such presentation is by the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Table 1. Profile of the Employees in terms of its Generational Divides

<i>Generational Divides</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Baby Boomers	6	7.59	4
Generation X	43	54.43	1
Millennials	22	27.85	2
Generation Z	8	10.13	3
Total	79	100	

The data presented in Table 1 reveals a significant generational difference among the respondents. Specifically, 43 out of 79 total respondents, or 54.43%, belong to Generation X, while only 6 respondents, or 7.59%, are from the Baby Boomer generation. It shows the demographic shifts in the workforce of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City.

The high percentage of Generation X respondents suggests that this cohort currently forms the backbone of the workforce. Generation X individuals, typically born between 1965 and 1980, are in the prime of their careers, holding significant numbers of mid to senior-level positions.

In contrast, the lower percentage of Baby Boomers born between 1946 and 1964 reflects their gradual exit from the workforce due to retirement. This demographic shift highlighted the ongoing transition as Baby Boomers retire and Generation X takes on more leadership and key roles.

McKinsey and Company (May 2023) state that workers across different age groups tend to leave or start new jobs for similar reasons, according to an analysis by senior partners Aaron De Smet and Bill Schaninger and colleagues. Younger workers favor flexibility, while older workers are more likely to cite compensation as the reason. This article shows the different perceptions of personnel relative to their age or generation. Each generation should be given a careful analysis to address the gaps or concerns in each age that could contribute to or hinder their productivity.

Table 2. Level of the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity in Terms of Responsiveness

<i>Items</i>	<i>Head</i>			<i>Employee</i>		
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. Willingness to help or assist with client’s	4.85	Very Satisfied	1	4.87	Very Satisfied	1

requests or concerns.						
2. Prompt service to clients	4.61	Very Satisfied	3	4.62	Very Satisfied	3
3. Readiness to respond to clients' inquiries	4.70	Very Satisfied	2	4.70	Very Satisfied	2
4. Informing clients about when the services will be performed	4.58	Very Satisfied	4	4.59	Very Satisfied	4
Composite Mean	4.68	Very Satisfied		4.70	Very Satisfied	
<i>4.45 – 5.00 – Very Satisfied 3.45 – 4.44 – Satisfied 2.45 – 3.44 – Undecided 1.45 – 2.44 – Dissatisfied 1.00 – 1.80 – Very Dissatisfied</i>						

As shown in Table no 2, the Head mark as “Very Satisfied” on the following items which include (1) Willingness to help or assist with client’s requests or concerns” with a mean score of 4.85; (2) Prompt service to clients inquiries” with the mean score of 4.61; (3) Readiness to respond to clients' inquiries with the mean score 4.70 and; (4) Informing clients about when the services will be performed with the mean score of 4.58. The composite mean of the level of the client’s satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in responsiveness as perceived by the head is 4.68, marked as “Very satisfied”.

The composite mean score of 4.68, marked as "Very Satisfied," reflects the overall high satisfaction level from the head's perspective regarding non-teaching personnel's responsiveness. This composite score aggregates the individual high scores across different items, indicating a consistent performance of their subordinates.

In addition, the Employees also graded themselves as “Very Satisfied” on the following items (1) Willingness to help or assist with client’s requests or concerns” with a mean score of 4.87; (2) Prompt service to clients' inquiries” with the mean score of 4.62; (3) Readiness to respond to clients' inquiries with the mean score 4.70 and; (4) Informing clients about when the services will be performed with the mean score of 4.59. The composite mean level of the client’s satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in responsiveness as perceived by the employees themselves is 4.70, marked as “Very satisfied”.

With a composite mean of 4.70, marked as "Very Satisfied," employees' self-assessment aligns closely with the head's perception. This consistency suggests a strong internal agreement on the high level of productivity and responsiveness. Janet (2018) emphasizes that customer responsiveness measures the speed and quality at which your company provides customer service and communication. According to Clint Fontanella (March 2023), a customer-responsive culture encourages agents to put the customer's needs first and create effective solutions as quickly as possible. A combination of speed and accuracy improves the team's overall productivity and generates delightful customer experiences. Nathalie Schooling’s article (October 2022) explains that responsiveness is the ability to act or respond quickly and effectively to a change or challenge.

Table 3. *Level of the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity in Terms of Reliability*

Items	Head			Employee		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
1. Accuracy of information Conveyed	4.52	Very Satisfied	2.5	4.32	Satisfied	3
2. Maintenance of error-free Records	4.35	Satisfied	4	4.23	Satisfied	4
3. Consistency of the service and assistance to requests	4.61	Very Satisfied	1	4.58	Very Satisfied	1
4. Dependability in handling clients' service problems	4.52	Very Satisfied	2.5	4.47	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.50	Very Satisfied		4.40	Satisfied	
<i>4.45 – 5.00 – Very Satisfied 3.45 – 4.44 – Satisfied 2.45 – 3.44 – Undecided 1.45 – 2.44 – Dissatisfied 1.00 – 1.80 – Very Dissatisfied</i>						

As shown in Table no 3, the following matters are perceived as “Very Satisfied” such as (1) Accuracy of information conveyed” with a mean score of 4.52; (2) Maintenance of error-free records with a mean score of 4.35; (3) Consistency of the service and assistance to requests with the mean score 4.61; (4) Dependability in handling clients' service problems with the mean score of 4.52. The average level of the client’s satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in terms of reliability as perceived by the head is 4.50 which is marked as “Very satisfied”.

Furthermore, the employees perceived themselves as “Satisfied” on the following items (1) Willingness to help or assist with clients’ requests or concerns” with a mean score of 4.32 and; (2) Prompt service to clients' inquiries” with a mean score of 4.23. On the other hand, the items marked as “Satisfied” include (3) Readiness to respond to clients' inquiries with a mean score of 4.58, and; (4) Informing clients about when the services will be performed with a mean score of 4.47 giving an overall average score of 4.40 “ in the level of the client’s satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in terms of reliability as perceived by the employees themselves. In an overall sense, reliability has a positive relationship in terms of productivity.

The close alignment between the head's and employees' ratings across all items indicates an interconnected understanding and shared commitment to client satisfaction within the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. Both perspectives marking their satisfaction as "Very Satisfied" emphasize the effectiveness and responsiveness of the non-teaching personnel. This high level of client satisfaction can be attributed to the personnel's willingness to assist, prompt service, readiness to respond, and clear communication about service timelines. The composite mean scores of 4.68 and 4.70 further justify this, reflecting a consistently high standard of service and client

satisfaction.

Sylvia Fronczak (February 2022) explains in her article that Reliability encompasses multiple facets that together provide a usable and dependable product for the customer because reliability focuses on their experience with your service. For example, if their service has an uptime of 99.999% over a time period but the customer experiences excessive latency or flaky behavior, the service lacks reliability.

Table 4. *Level of the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity in Terms of Communication*

Items	Head			Employee		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
1. Attentive listening to what the client says or what they have to say	4.78	Very Satisfied	1	4.76	Very Satisfied	1
2. Effectivity and clarity of response	4.54	Very Satisfied	3	4.46	Very Satisfied	3
3. Patience, calmness, and friendly demeanor.	4.57	Very Satisfied	2	4.63	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.63	Very Satisfied		4.62	Very Satisfied	

.45 – 5.00 – Very Satisfied | 3.45 – 4.44 – Satisfied | 2.45 – 3.44 – Undecided | 1.45 – 2.44 – Dissatisfied | 1.00 – 1.80 – Very Dissatisfied

Based on Table no 4, the Head assessed their employees as “Very Satisfied” in terms of Communication with an average score of 4.63. The scores of the Head are as follows: (1) Attentive listening to what the client says or what they have to say with a mean score of 4.78; (2) Effectivity and clarity of response with a mean score of 4.54; and (3) Patience, calmness, and friendly demeanor with a mean scores 4.57.

Furthermore, employees also assessed themselves as “Very Satisfied” in terms of Communication with an average score of 4.62. The scores of the Employees are as follows: (1) Attentive listening to what the client says or what they have to say with a mean score of 4.76; (2) Effectivity and clarity of response with a mean score of 4.46; and (3) Patience, calmness, and friendly demeanor with a mean scores 4.63.

The data from Table 4 shows that both the head and employees rate communication highly, with both groups expressing "Very Satisfied" levels of satisfaction. The close orientation in their assessments shows a well-established culture of effective communication within the organization. This culture likely contributes to high client satisfaction and effective internal and external interactions. The specific high scores in attentive listening, clarity of response, and maintaining a positive demeanor indicate that these are key strengths in the communication practices of the non-teaching personnel at the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. This good communication supports the overall effectiveness and responsiveness of the organization in addressing client needs.

Based on Study.com (2022), Customer service communication is the exchange of information between a company and a customer to address the customer's needs. Effective communication is critical as it shows the customers that the representatives understand them rather than just listening to what they say. Some of these skills required for effective customer service include speaking politely, efficiently, effectively, and clearly. Relatively, effective communication is one of the factors that keeps the clients satisfied even then there are times that they do not get the answers they need or want.

Table 5. *Level of the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity in Terms of Integrity*

Items	Head			Employee		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
1. Fair treatment and keeping good relationships with clients	4.73	Very Satisfied	2	4.78	Very Satisfied	1
2. With a sense of honesty in the delivery of information	4.75	Very Satisfied	1	4.75	Very Satisfied	3
3. With a sense of accountability to his/her word and actions	4.67	Very Satisfied	3	4.76	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.71	Very Satisfied		4.76	Very Satisfied	

.45 – 5.00 – Very Satisfied | 3.45 – 4.44 – Satisfied | 2.45 – 3.44 – Undecided | 1.45 – 2.44 – Dissatisfied | 1.00 – 1.80 – Very Dissatisfied

As shown in Table No. 5, the heads perceived their subordinates as “Very Satisfied” in terms of Integrity with an overall mean score of 4.71. All the items are responded to as “Very Satisfied” by the Head which includes (1) Fair treatment and keeping good relationships with clients with a mean score of 4.73; (2) With a sense of honesty in the delivery of information with a mean score of 4.75; and (3) With a sense of accountability to his/her word and actions with a mean score of 4.67.

Moreover, the Employees also assessed themselves as “Very Satisfied” in all the items under Integrity including 1) Fair treatment and keeping good relationships with clients with a mean score of 4.78; (2) With a sense of honesty in the delivery of information with a mean score of 4.75; and (3) With a sense of accountability to his/her word and actions with a mean score of 4.76. Thus, giving a mean score of 4.76 marked as “Very Satisfied” by the employees.

The data from Table No. 5 indicates that both heads and employees perceive a high level of integrity within the organization. Both groups marking themselves as "Very Satisfied," highlight a strong, collective commitment to ethical behavior and accountability. These high ratings in fair treatment, honesty, and accountability not only reflect key strengths of the non-teaching personnel at the Schools

Division Office of San Pedro City but also strengthen the overall effectiveness and responsiveness of the organization in serving its clients.

Based on the article of Indeed (2023), in a workplace setting, acting with integrity often means demonstrating your core values in all efforts. Here are a few behaviors that show integrity: (1) being dependable and following through on commitments; (2) being open and honest when communicating with others; and (3) holding yourself accountable and owning up to your shortcomings.

Table 6. *Level of the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity in Terms of Outcome*

Items	Head			Employee		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
1. Making sure they deliver on their responsibilities.	4.58	Very Satisfied	3	4.52	Very Satisfied	2
2. Providing services as promised	4.65	Very Satisfied	2	4.47	Very Satisfied	3
3. Handles issues with professionalism	4.72	Very Satisfied	1	4.81	Very Satisfied	1
Composite Mean	4.65	Very Satisfied		4.60	Very Satisfied	

.45 – 5.00 – Very Satisfied | 3.45 – 4.44 – Satisfied | 2.45 – 3.44 – Undecided | 1.45 – 2.44 – Dissatisfied | 1.00 – 1.80 – Very Dissatisfied

Tabulated in Table no.6, the Heads assessed their employees as “Very Satisfied” on the following items which include (1) Making sure they deliver on their responsibilities with a mean score of 4.58; (2) Providing services as promised with a mean score of 4.65; and (3) Handles issues with professionalism with the mean scores of 4.58, 4.65 and 4.72 respectively. As a result, it gives the mean level of satisfaction as 4.65 or “Very satisfied” to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in terms of Outcome.

Furthermore, the Employees also graded themselves as “Very Satisfied” on the following items (1) Making sure they deliver on their responsibilities with a mean score of 4.52; (2) Providing services as promised with a mean score of 4.47; and (3) Handles issues with professionalism with a mean score of 4.81. The composite mean level of the client’s satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity in terms of Outcome as perceived by the employees themselves is 4.60 which is marked as “Very Satisfied”.

The high levels of satisfaction in various aspects of productivity in terms of the outcome of the services reflect a strong, effective organizational culture at the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. In the table, Professionalism ranked as no. 1 where clients are most satisfied if issues are being handled well. It not only resolves problems efficiently but also leaves a positive impression on clients, fostering trust and confidence. The mutual recognition of key strengths and the slight differences in self-assessment highlight areas for potential growth and continuous improvement, ensuring that the organization remains effective, reliable, and client-focused.

As mentioned by Phil Fryer Ward (2023), business outcomes are, in essence, the goals set by a company to measure the success or achievement of an internal or external process. These goals can also be labeled “desired outcomes” and are a useful way of helping staff to focus on achieving customer success. In the article on LinkedIn (August 2023), service outcomes are the measurable and observable effects of your customer service on your customers, your organization, and your stakeholders. They can be positive or negative, intended or unintended, and short-term or long-term. Some examples of service outcomes are customer satisfaction, loyalty, retention, referrals, complaints, feedback, quality, efficiency, and reputation. Likewise, one of the outcomes of the Division Office is the Client’s satisfaction through offering quality service to all the clients of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City. This is the main priority of the Division, especially for the teaching personnel, so they can focus more on teaching children effectively.

Table 7. *Relationship Between the Responses of the Head And Employee on the Client’s Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel’s Productivity*

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Responsiveness	0.18	0.02363	Reject Ho	Significant
Reliability	0.46	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Communication	0.22	0.00548	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Integrity	0.25	0.00154	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Outcome	0.19	0.01680	Reject Ho	Significant

As gleaned in Table 7, when the responses of the head and employee respondents on the client’s satisfaction with the Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity were compared, the computed r-value of 0.46 for reliability, 0.22 for communication, and 0.25 for integrity have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. In addition, the computed r-value of 0.18 for responsiveness and 0.19 for outcome have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely implied that the responses of the head and employee respondents on the client’s satisfaction of the Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel’s productivity have highly significant relationships in terms of reliability, communication, and integrity; and significant relationships in terms of responsiveness and outcome.

Reponsiveness and outcome show weaker correlations compared to reliability, communication, and integrity but they still exhibit

significant positive relationships between head and employee perceptions. Responsiveness and outcome have a significant relationship with client satisfaction because they directly influence clients' experiences and perceptions of the organization's services and immediate action can be taken. The remaining three variables: reliability, communication, and integrity have highly significant relationships because even if their impact may be more indirect, it is experienced for a long term, resulting in stronger relationships to the productivity of the personnel in this specific context.

According to Talentlyft (2023), despite the benefits, flexible work arrangements can provide too much employee freedom and cut their productivity. This study shows that there is a negative relationship between the implementation of flexible work arrangements to the employee's productivity. It means that aside from the positive results, an organization may also gain a negative result from it.

Contrary to the Talentlyft's study, this research shows that there is a highly significant relationship between the Flexible Work Arrangement to the employees' productivity in terms of reliability, communication, and integrity and a significant relationship in terms of responsiveness and outcome.

Table 8. *Relationship between the Level of the Employee's Generational Divide and the Client's Satisfaction of Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to Non-Teaching Personnel's Productivity*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Responsiveness	0.01	0.90076	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Reliability	0.21	0.00809	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Communication	0.02	0.80303	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Integrity	0.16	0.04463	Reject Ho	Significant
Outcome	0.16	0.04463	Reject Ho	Significant

As displayed in Table 8, when the responses of the head and employee respondents on the client's satisfaction with the Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity were compared to their generational divides, the computed r-value of 0.21 for reliability has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Additionally, the computed r-value of 0.16 for both integrity and outcome have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Meanwhile, the computed r-value of 0.01 for responsiveness and 0.02 for communication have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely signified that the responses of the head and employee respondents on the client's satisfaction of the Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity have high significant relationships for reliability; significant relationships for integrity and outcome; and no significant relationships for responsiveness and communication when compared based to their generational divides.

There are varying degrees of association between generational divides and client satisfaction dimensions as shown in the table. It is shown that there is a statistically highly significant relationship in terms of reliability. Older employees with longer tenures may have established reputations for reliability based on years of consistent performance and reliability while younger employees, who have shorter tenures, may still be building their reputations for reliability and may be evaluated differently based on their track record and experience.

For integrity, older generations may place strong importance on traditional values such as honesty and accountability and may view integrity as crucial for maintaining trust and credibility in professional relationships. For example, Gen X who are known to be self-reliant and self-directed, are expected to be more independent in doing their tasks.

On the other hand, younger generations may also prioritize integrity but interpret it differently. They may value transparency, authenticity, and social responsibility in organizational practices. Integrity and outcome exhibit slightly weaker but still significant relationships. Conversely, responsiveness and communication demonstrate negligible relationships with generational divides. These findings underscore the importance of considering generational differences when addressing client satisfaction and tailoring strategies to meet different generations' diverse needs and expectations.

Based from Matt Gonzales (May 2023), given the example stated by Erica Lasan, says that tensions are growing between Baby Boomers and Generation Z workers—and conflicting perspectives on work are to blame. This study shows that the generational divide among employees affects their decisions and perspective when it comes to work and this includes reliability, integrity, and outcome which are

In Adam Hayes' study (June 2022), he refers to a generation gap as the chasm that separates the beliefs and behaviors belonging to members of two different generations. More specifically, a generation gap can describe the differences in thoughts, actions, and tastes exhibited by members of younger generations versus older ones which supports that there is a possible effect of the employees' age on how the heads and employees themselves view and execute their jobs in terms of Reliability such as the accuracy and error-free of the information they give to their clients, how consistent and dependable their services are. Moreover, when it comes to integrity, the generational gap among the employees is possibly a contributing factor to how the employees treat their clients and how they honestly deliver the information and be held accountable for their actions as perceived by their department heads and themselves. Lastly, in terms of outcome, the age gap could have a potential effect on the delivery of the expected outcome from the employees and how the personnel handle the issues with professionalism.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the generational divide and the client's satisfaction as perceived by the head and employees in terms of responsiveness and communication. Individuals who share a particular generation and generational personality frequently have similar views on many issues such as religion, politics, family, work-life balance, and work ethic. Differing views on these topics exist across generations, causing clash points or conflicts in the workplace that affect recruitment, retention, training, productivity, customer service, and organizational morale (Mona Sedrak, Ph.D, et al., 2019).

In the case of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City, the personnel generational divide that falls in Generation X (28 to 43 years old) which is more than half of the population shows that the majority of the employees explain that the age does not affect the client's satisfaction in terms of Responsiveness and Communication perceived by this group of people and their heads.

Conclusion

Through a comprehensive analysis of the study, the following discussion encapsulates the central conclusion and underscores the broader implications for organizational policy and future inquiry. (1) Majority of the employees of the Schools Division of San Pedro City belonged to Generation X who are known to be self-reliant, self-directed, and autonomous. They are expected to be more independent in doing their tasks while few employees are baby boomers who are experienced, competitive, and self-assured. The distribution of the employees in the different generational divides has a great impact on the way they do their jobs which may result in different outcomes. (2) The researcher gets the perception of the department heads and the employees' evaluation of themselves to identify the possible outcome of their work. In the study, it is shown that both the heads and the employees agreed that they are serving a satisfactory to a very satisfactory level on the non-teaching personnel's productivity in terms of responsiveness, reliability, communication, integrity, and outcome. Through this positive result, it is shown that the non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division Office of San Pedro provide good service to their clients and deliver a very satisfactory service. (3) The Schools Division Office of San Pedro City's heads and employees implied highly significant relationships in terms of reliability, communication, and integrity; and significant relationships in terms of responsiveness and outcome to non-teaching personnel's productivity. The decision in all the given variables is to reject the null hypothesis which means that there are significant relationships between heads and employees on the client's satisfaction of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity. (5) All the employees of the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City are in a flexible work arrangement, no significant relationship existed between their responses on the client's satisfaction with the Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity in terms of reliability, communication, and integrity, and significant relationship in terms of responsiveness and outcome.

This means that flexible work arrangement implementation is effective in boosting good results in the personnel's productivity. (6) The responses of the head and employee respondents on the client's satisfaction of Schools Division Office in San Pedro City to non-teaching personnel's productivity have highly significant relationships for reliability; significant relationships for integrity and outcome; and no significant relationships for responsiveness and communication when compared based to their generational divides.

The study showed three of the variables resulted from rejecting the null hypothesis which are reliability, integrity, and outcome. While two of the variables failed to reject the null hypothesis, these two variables are responsiveness and communication. Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the researcher has arrived at the following recommendations: (1) Implementing rules such as flexible work arrangements in offices and other ventures are highly recommended. With this, our law makers that may call the FLEXIWORK Act of 2024 must give importance to providing clear implementing rules that every company or agency must follow.

Establish a clear and comprehensive flexible work policy that outlines the types of flexible work arrangements available, such as remote work, flexible hours, compressed workweeks, or possible job sharing. They must focus on the time it is possible to be considered in the offices, and the protection of the employees and the employers from which both parties may benefit. The employees may have the choice to decide on what working scheme they can work the best. This promotes self-productivity and will result in a much more positive outcome for the organization. (2) All the employees in all generational divides are encouraged to follow and, should extend an effort to adapt to the flexible work arrangement because it shows a positive impact on the outcomes of their work. Offer training programs to help employees adjust to flexible work arrangements. This can include time management workshop, training on using remote work tools, and stress management resources. The following interventions are suggested to be followed. Baby Boomers could be more equipped by using different online video conferencing platforms in that way they can utilize the use of flexible work arrangements as well as Generation X which shows that majority of the workforce is in this generational divide age range. Exposing themselves to the power and works of these online applications can help them be encouraged and it may have a big impact once they are aware of their uses. A training entitled OPLAN CATCH UP WITH THE NEW TRENDS with a small group of participants will help them realize that even at their age, they can still use the full potential of these applications. It aims to holistically assist different age levels using the most updated and most useful applications across all ages. (3) Create standardized communication protocols to ensure that all employees, regardless of the work arrangement, can effectively communicate with each other and their clients. The Division can use different methods including regular virtual meetings, updates via email or internal platforms, and clear guidelines for availability and response times. Consistent communication is needed to uphold the high standards of service and responsiveness and ensure that client inquiries and concerns are addressed promptly. (4) Invest in strong and user-friendly technology solutions that facilitate remote work and flexible schedules, such as collaborative tools, or maximizing the use of Microsoft Teams or other technology, project management software (ex: Asana), and secure remote access systems. These tools can help non-teaching personnel

maintain the high levels of responsiveness and prompt service that clients expect, even when working remotely or during flexible hours. (5) The heads may consider studying the characteristics of different generational divides. With this, they can easily know how the employees have their own work style. Also, it will help them to decide what kind of workloads may be given to specific employees and how properly they should be treated. Also, the heads may provide implementing rules and regulations in the proceedings of the flexible work arrangement. It is a protection to the company as well that the employees must bear in mind in following the schools' activities. (6) Future researchers may consider conducting this same study in a qualitative form where there is a specific basis for the assessment of Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction. This will help provide more ideas and findings from the respondents and will get full access to their perspectives as the heads, employees, or even the clients. It is also recommended to study possible related topics such as: Relationship of the Perspective of the Employees to the Client's Perception of the Services to the Implementation of Flexible Work Arrangement. The Effects of Implementing Flexible Work Arrangements in All the Different Aspects of the Business or the Offices.

References

- Briscoe, K. (August 2019). Integrity in Business - A Priceless Essential for Success
- Birt, J. (March 2023). 9 Types of Flexible Working Arrangements (Pros and Cons) Indeed (2023). Integrity in the Workplace: Definition and Examples
- Chambers, S. (October 2021). 10 Tips To Improve Customer Service Communication, pp 11-12
- Cherry, K. (May 2023). Understanding Social Exchange Theory in Psychology.
- Gonzales, M. (May 2023). The Generational Divide Between Older and Younger Employees
- Gothelf, J. (February 2023). What's The Difference Between A User Outcome And A Business Outcome?<https://jeffgothelf.com/blog/difference-between-user-outcome-and-business-outcome/>
- Hayes, A. (June 2022). Generation Gap: What It Is and Why It's Important to Business
- Indeed (2023). Service Quality: Definition, 5 Dimensions and Implementation<https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/service-quality>
- InitiativeOne (September 2022). Are Generational Differences That Important to Workplace Culture?<https://www.initiativeone.com/post/generational-differences-in-the-workplace>
- Janet (August 2018). Customer responsiveness: What it is & how do I improve it?
- Juneja, P., (2015). Management Study Guide Content Team.
- Lesonsky, R. (November 2019). 7 Ways To Be More Responsive To Your Customers
- Leedy, P. D., Ormand, E. O. (2013). Correlational research. Practical Research: Planning and Design.
- LinkedIn (August 2023), How do you evaluate service outcomes for better results?<https://www.linkedin.com/advice/0/how-do-you-evaluate-service-outcomes>.
- Mckinsey and Company (May 2023). What generational divide?<https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/sustainable-inclusive-growth/chart-of-the-day>
- NuEditor (October 2017). The Importance Of Speed, Accuracy, And Reliability In Customer Service The Essential Guide to Improving Service Reliability
- Perry, E. (June 2022), What's integrity in the workplace and why is it important? (+examples)
- Rozlan, A., Nur, Z. (November 2020). The Impact of Flexible Working Arrangements on Millennials: A Conceptual Analysis
- Sylvia Fronczak (February 2022), The Essential Guide to Improving Service Reliability, pp 43-48
- Schooling, N. (October 2022). The Importance of Responsiveness<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-responsiveness-n-lighten>
- Talentlyf (2023). What is Flexible Work Arrangements?<https://www.talentlyft.com/en/resources/what-is-flexible-work-arrangements>
- The Insider (May 2023). Communication skills for customer service and why they're important<https://www.glion.edu/magazine/communication-skills-customer-service>
- Vonfintel, S. (November 2022). Effective Communication in Customer Service<https://study.com/learn/lesson/effective-communication-customer-service>
- Waltower, S. (October 2023). Why Do Employees Prefer Flexible Work Arrangements?

Ward, P. (2023). Achieving business outcomes with service excellence <https://servicemuse.com/business-outcomes-using-service/>

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